

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK:

THE MEANINGS OF LONG-TERM CARE AND QUALITY OF CARE IN DENMARK

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Contents

The meanings of long-term care and quality of care in Denmark	4
Brief summary	4
1. Definitions and structure	4
2. Boundaries	6
3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation	7
4. Stakeholders, Governance including quality of care.....	7
5. Territorial Differentiation.....	12
6. Debates, Strategies	12
Annex 1	16

The meanings of long-term care and quality of care in Denmark

Brief summary

This report focuses on what LTC is in Denmark and especially on the discussion of what quality of care is and can be understood as. Besides, focus is on a short depiction of the LTC care system on how to understand quality of care. There is no single and uniform depiction of how to understand the concept.

1. Definitions and structure

Denmark is seen as belong to the Nordic welfare state model implying a universal approach to long-term care, but also with attempts to ensure equality in access to social care (van Gerven 2022; Kangas and Kvist 2019; Greve and Béland 2022). This is also the case for long-term care implying that even if there are a few private actors, the role of the market in Denmark is limited compared to that of other countries, with the exception of support for cleaning in private homes.

Long-term care can be challenged by economic and other crisis reducing public sector income given that it is mainly a state issue (Greve et al. 2021; Greve et al. 2024). One implication of this being that the main focus here will be on the role of the public sector and how this relates to different actors' perception of the long-term care system. EU's rules at the outset does not have any impact on the long-term care system in Denmark.

There is no precise and overarching definition of what LTC is, and in principle it can cover all age groups, albeit here the focus is mainly related to those who have reached the age of retirement. There can and will be in the Danish welfare states local variations and differences in the understanding among key actors within the field and variation in the level of services available within different municipalities. Focus in Denmark is especially on the social part of long-term care,

e.g. health care is often not central for the understanding of quality of care, albeit there is contact between the health care system and the long-term care system.

The basic principles for long-term care are:

“Separate universal, residence-based and tax-financed scheme, providing in-kind and cash benefits (the Citizen-controlled personal assistance (Borgerstyret personlig assistance) is provided in the form of subsidies).

Every resident is entitled to in-kind personal and practical assistance if s/he cannot perform the basic personal and practical activities autonomously, regardless of ability to pay.

The system of care services is decentralized: the responsibility for the provision of personal and practical assistance and necessary accommodation rests with the local authorities. They must consider all requests for personal and practical assistance. The decisions of the local authorities must be based on a specific and individual assessment of the need for assistance. Complaints about decisions on personal and practical assistance must be addressed to the National Social Appeals Board.”¹

Thus, this points towards the fact that the understanding of long-term care in Denmark has to be based upon a number of elements, including local variations in how it is implemented and prioritized given the local economic options.

The following will further mainly focus on the social care of long-term care. This as health care in Denmark, universal as in other countries, mainly focus on broader health care issues, and not on long-term care. Still, there are a very few elements related to health care that municipalities do have the responsibility for. This includes rehabilitation as well that those living in old-age homes getting support to, for example, take their medicine. If the elderly are in need of health care, a general practitioner will be called upon and if urgent the elderly will be sent to a hospital. Palliative care can be done at home, but also at a few specific institutions in Denmark.

¹ Here from [Comparative tables - MISSOC](#)

2. Boundaries

Long-term care in Denmark is financed out of general taxation. The municipalities pay for long-term care and get their economic resources in a combination of a municipality income tax and state block grants. The block grants to municipalities are based upon a number of criteria. They are, in short, related to where there in an objective way can be expected to be a relation between the criteria and the municipality's expenditures. This includes, for example, the local demographic composition, but also the level of unemployment, housing types and proportion of people without further education.

There is for long-term care in private homes no user charges in Denmark, and there is no estimation of what people overall buy of supplementary long-term care services, such as cleaning, gardening etc. There have been the options that people could from the public as well as private providers of cleaning and personal care buy extra services and pay for this. However, the evaluation of these has shown that this has only been used very limited (S. Foged, Hjelmar, and Jonsen 2021; Brogaard and Hjelmar 2014). This can reflect the cost of the services as this shall be market based, and many elderly are most likely not prepared to pay for it or not prioritizing using their economic resources for these services. Elderly living in homes for elderly will have to pay renting costs in the same way as if they were living by themselves.

There is no indication that there has been a decline in the real level of spending on old age in Denmark, and by this there has been taking into consideration the increase in the number of elderly, albeit locally there might be variations due to a combination of different local priorities and economic options.

Stakeholders that are important is the state, the municipalities (and their central organisation), trade unions organising the staff employed in the municipalities and different users' organisations. The private sector has a limited role, albeit some would prefer to have a stronger role for the private sector with regard to delivery based upon an argument of the impact of using market types mechanism. There is only very limited information about the degree to which those not eligible for public support buys, for example, cleaning and other services.

3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation

There is a relatively large number of data available in Denmark with regard to LTC. This relates to spending, number of hours, how many people is living in long-term care homes, etc.

In annex 1 is an overview of general accessible data from the Danish Statistical Authorities (www.dst.dk). In several of these there is also access to regional and data for all municipalities.

They also provide information (so far only for 2022) on elderly who have been granted home help, the number of hours etc.

User satisfaction can be found, among others in (Social 2024), where measurement of quality is argued to be difficult, but that user survey can be one type of indicator.

There is information on many areas of both central and local government spending and services, often with a focus on the local level given they have the administrative responsibility.

The size of informal care is less clearly covered by indicators also given the delimitation between when it is informal care and when it is a continuation of the split of work between partners in a private home. A few survey data on the impacts for people providing informal care is available. However, for the informal care it seems that this impact is higher for women as historically, women live longer than men.

Comparable data from OECD is available. Overall, Denmark is one of the high spenders with regard to long-term care.

4. Stakeholders, Governance including quality of care

Central stakeholders in relation to provision are, as already indicated earlier, the state and municipalities. They can be influenced by different interest groups representing users, employees and civil society.

There is no simple and clear definition of what the understanding of quality of care is neither in the central regulation, nor in the different municipalities in Denmark. This has also been confirmed in the interviews with stakeholders. One therefore has to look into what types of keywords are used when presenting and referring to the quality of care delivered.

Donabedian's approach might be a way to look into quality of care, (Avedis Donabedian 1988), with a focus on structure, process and outcome (ibid p. 1745), who also finds that measurement might include "all actions taken to establish, protect, promote and improve the quality of health care" (A. Donabedian 2003, xxiiiv).

Quality of care can in a more general way include:

- Effectiveness and care safety
- Patient-centeredness and responsiveness
- Care co-ordination (Greve 2016, 3)

Choice is often argued to be a quality element given that it empowers the users to choose based upon their preferences (Rostgaard 2017). This report also included that quality element for practical support in private homes could be continuity and worker continuity. This has also been confirmed in the interviews with stakeholders. In an interview a stakeholder for example emphasized the importance of continuity in the relation between the long-term care worker and the citizen who receive help: "and then relational stability. In other words, if the condition for, like, really succeeding with activating care, is also to support progression. In reality it is that you have some stable and lasting relationships with citizens/long-term care users".

In relation to continuity two stakeholders stated that it does not necessarily need to be the same long-term care worker who visits a person, the most important is that the long-term care worker know what help is needed: "it is not always so important that it is the same one who comes. What is

crucial is that they know what to help with. (...) they must know why they are at this person's home and what kind of person they are coming in to". It is thus professional stability which is the most decisive as a stakeholder stated it, and in this regard several stakeholders mentioned the importance of educated staff for providing proper help.

A report on possible indicators of quality argued that the following could be elements related to quality: "Citizen safety and health, outcomes for the individual citizen, organizational quality and citizen-experienced quality" (own translation) (Rambøll 2018, 4). However, despite it was a preliminary attempt to define quality indicators there is still no national common indicators of quality, albeit user survey seems to be used in every municipality as an indicator on the satisfaction of care and this is then used as an indicator of the quality of care and possible change over time herein. Thus, user satisfaction is seemingly one indicator of quality, although this can be difficult to get from people with dementia.

Dignity has been another core concept used in relation to care and quality of care. Dignity is seen in relation to issues such as quality of life and self-determination. Where quality of life can be considered as related to a "meaningful every day, feel of joy, security and connections" and self-determination related to the feeling that citizens can live "the life they themselves wish" (Røgeskov, Jensen, and Hjorth-Enemark 2023, 17) (own translation). These elements can change depending on the specific circumstances, and the citizen's wishes might be in conflict with the care delivered and the way this can be carried out in the different municipalities.

Dignity was also a word that was mentioned during the stakeholder interviews when talking about quality of care. It was often related to having an influence on the help received: "and that [a good care] is largely about an independent and dignified life, and being involved and experiencing that you (...) are the one who controls your own life, right?".

In describing the ideal care a stakeholder emphasised the importance of both having your physical and mental needs being fulfilled, "and if the two things go hand in hand (...) then I would say we can talk about a dignified care for the elderly".

Furthermore, the word 'dignified' was mentioned in relation to the professional help provided: "And I don't think it [the care] can be dignified without us also ensuring professionalism into it. Because providing dignified care and concern has a professional aspect to it."

Dignity is also part of the changed legislation in Denmark in the late 2024.

Another policy report (Indenrigs- og sundhedsministeriet 2019), argued that possible themes for quality indicators could revolve around: 1) Functional abilities, 2) Life-quality and satisfaction, and 3) Coherence and predictability. However, user survey, for example, might be less useful in a number of municipalities given the relatively few numbers of persons receiving different types of care. It seems that the only central analysis carried out has been a national user survey of satisfaction with the long-term care services. This further due to the fact that a number of elderly living in homes for elderly are persons with dementia wherefrom it might be difficult to get reliable answers from.

In relation to a meeting concerning the field of care for the elderly in 2021 Sundhedsstyrelsen prepared a paper on the process with regard to the development of quality indicators. Differences can occur depending on the professional quality (faglig kvalitet) in the treatment, care and rehabilitation. Lastly, there might be organisational quality (Sundhedsstyrelsen 2021, 8), albeit the more precise description of quality and indicators to measure this cannot be found in the report by Sundhedsstyrelsen.

Influence and self-determination including flexibility in the delivery of long-term care might also be an issue related to the quality of care. Continuity and good relations between users and employees have also been argued to be an element. However, these relations have also been criticized as they can be conflictual. (Pedersen 2024). These aspects were also highlighted in several of our stakeholder interviews as mentioned earlier in this report.

A specific issue might be the quality of life of the elderly. This might be an indicator of the quality of services, albeit the causality can be difficult to depict. A report points towards using ASCOT as an indicator of quality of life. This includes control over daily life, personal care and well-being, food and drink, safety, social contact, activities, housing and dignity (Amilon, Lauritzen, and

Christensen 2024). The analysis also indicated that a larger group of elderly with fewer social contacts often received practical help in their private home.

Elderly in Denmark are in general satisfied with the support they get according to a user survey from 2021². User surveys can be one way of trying to depict satisfaction with the quality of care, albeit naturally this is not an objective measure of the quality of care, and the subjective answers thereby not a strong indication of the quality of care.

One element in the quality of care has been argued to be users' opportunity to make choices, including who shall do the cleaning and deliver the support at home and other elements. However, as an article showed (S. K. Foged and Houlberg 2023) a voucher market, which could be one way to provide users with choice, might, without price competition, imply that the production cost will be increased with regard to practical help as this is what was studied. There might further be regional differences given that the possibility of making a choice might vary across areas with many and few providers of long-term care services. This is also due to the fact that there are economies of scale of public production. Still, in an agreement of change in the long-term care system, choice of what type of service, and influence on what kind of service being provided one day is argued to be a quality³, including strong influence of the users. The precise implementation and legal changes still have to be passed through the parliament.

Overall, there are a number of words used to try to emphasize what good care is, albeit not always very precise and also often without including the risk and problems associated with these approaches. This includes the legal position of the users, e.g. it shall be possible to check whether the promised care is delivered. Furthermore, there are often differences in perceptions among users and providers about what is needed as care.

² [Brugertilfredshedsundersøgelse for hjemmepleje](#)

³ https://www.sm.dk/Media/638490573249130235/Aeldrereform_aftaletekst_apr2024.pdf.

In general, the issue of quality of care relates to the formal public sector delivery of care, and less to the informal care provided. The latter is also due to the fact that in a number of cases it is continuation of support among people living together.

5. Territorial Differentiation

There are territorial differences, which can be depicted from the data sources as shown in Annex 1. The differences relate to that municipalities have some degree of freedom to decide the level of support, but also that there can be variations in the economic option for municipalities.

The differing conditions, varying from municipality to municipality, was also mentioned in several of our stakeholder interviews: "there is a lot of difference between municipalities, and this "postcode show". In other words, some municipalities have a certain level of service, other municipalities may have a different level of service. So, you can be citizens with the same needs on two sides of a municipal border. And then it can be very different what you are offered."

6. Debates, Strategies

The elements of quality as presented in the previous sections is also important for the current debates of quality. The core debates thus continue to relate to the aspects such as choice and continuity in care, as well as the level of services. User survey as mentioned above seems to be one indicator of the level of quality.

There are also debates about the use of new technology, including whether users will have to buy and use robot-cleaners themselves instead of receiving a visit from a social worker. In the interviews with stakeholders welfare technology are received positively and it was mentioned by several stakeholders that the technology can both help as a way of making the long-term care users more self-sufficient, as well as being a help for the long-term care workers, for example preventing work-related injuries. One stakeholder mentioned that the core of the debate revolves around the importance of the people receiving long term care to not *only* receive help from technology, and the dilemma in finding a balance between the two:

"(...) and then there is the whole technological part, there are some things that can be taken care of by some welfare technology, so that we use the employees we can get, in the right way, or where you can say here must it be a human contact, or here you can't put in a technology to replace. (...) But there is also some culture and some understanding that, can technology also sometimes replace the human relationship? Because we also have to say that some of the benefits of home care in everyday life are just as much the experience for long-term care user, that someone actually comes to me. That is, this human relation. So how do we replace that? Or how do we provide it in a different way via a screen, for example?"

Overall, there is a constant ongoing discussion on the level of services, and what types of changes can increase the level of services, bearing in mind that due to demographic changes there will be an increase in the number of users in the years to come – and the risk of insufficient qualified staff to handle it.

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Annex 1

From the Danish Statistical Office (www.dst.dk).

● Social services for senior citizens

- .. VH33 Private suppliers of home help by region (2008-2022)
- .. AED08 Recipients of Training and Maintenance Training by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2008-2022)
- .. AED10A Recipients of preventative home visits by region, home visits, age and sex (2016-2022)
- .. AED19A Length of stay (days) for persons aged 67, by region, unit and diagnosis. (2014-2022)
- .. AED20A Clinical pathways and readmissions for persons aged 67, by region, unit and diagnosis (2012-2022)
- .. AED21 Service indicators (per cent of all individuals) by region and services (2008-2022)
- .. REHAB19 Recipients of rehabilitation by region, age and sex (2019-2022)
- .. LABY20 Recipients to home care, 67 years and over (per cent of the population) by municipality groups and services (2022)

Assessed need for home care

- .. AED022 Home care, free choice (referral hours per week) by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2008-2022)
- .. AED021 Home care, free choice (referral hours average per week per recipients) by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2008-2022)
- .. AED06 Recipients referral to home care, free choice, by region, type of benefits, hours per week, age and sex (2008-2022)
- .. AED14 Recipients referral to home care, free choice, who change contractor by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2009-2022)
- .. AED12 Recipients referral to home care, free choice, who use private contractor by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2008-2022)
- .. AED13 First-time referred recipients, free choice, who use private contractor, by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2010-2022)

Gender equality indicator, Assessed need for home care

- .. LIGEH12 Gender equality indicator of persons referred to home care by region, age and family type (2010-2022)
- .. LIGEH13 Gender equality indicator of hours of home care (average) by region, age and family type (2010-2022)

Home care provided

- .. AED01 Home care, free choice (provided hours per week) by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2011-2022)
- .. AED02 Home care, free choice (provided hours average per week) by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2011-2022)
- .. AED023 Recipients of home care, free choice, by region, type of benefits, hours per week, age and sex (2011-2022)
- .. AED012 Recipients of home care, free choice, who use private contractor by region, type of benefits, age and sex (2013-2022)

Housing for senior citizens

- .. AED16 Free choice of dwelling and average waiting time for nursing homes/nursing dwellings for persons aged 67 and older by region (2009-2022)
- .. AED07 Recipients referred to home care at nursing homes/nursing dwellings by region, age and sex (2008-2022)

